

ProSmallAgriMed is a project approved and funded under the PRIMA programme.

The application was completed in 2020
 Section 2 – Multitopic
 Approved in December 2020.

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- Démarche intégrée pour l'obtention d'aliments de qualité (QUALISUD)
- Marchés, Organisations, Institutions et Stratégies d'Acteurs (MOISA)
- Qualiplante

- Università del Piemonte Orientale, Alessandria
- Università di Palermo
- Council for Agricultural Research and Economics - CREA

- Institut National Agronomique de Tunisie (INAT)

- Université Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah

- Université Badji-Mokhtar Annaba
- ANVREDET/Projet PLANTAbiotek (Agence Nationale de Valorisation des Résultats de la Recherche et du Développement Technologique)
- Tchimbo

The aim of this proposal is to **increase yield and yield stability for small farmers** by implementing agronomic practices through the promotion of the rational use of **beneficial soil microbiota** and their positive effects on productivity of **inter-cropped perennial** (cactus pear) **and short-term species** (field crops and winter-grown vegetables).

Impacts include:

- (i) increased soil cover, with direct implication for the accumulation of organic matter and water retention ability, which directly boost soil fertility;
- (ii) lower environmental pollution through reduction of chemical inputs;
- (iii) development of an agro-microbial industry in North Africa;
- (iv) setting up of intercropping systems that can increase at the same time both yield and yield stability.

The call of the project focused on re-designing the agro-livelihood systems to ensure resilience.

We have chosen to rely on three main lines:

Cactus pear (*Opuntia ficus-indica*)

This is a species well known for its ability to grow in arid and semi-arid areas.

In addition to its edible fruits, it can be a source of various products (oil, pigments, etc.) and it is used as feed.

Intercropping with annual coltures

Cactus pear plants, which are perennial, will be grown with annual plants in order to increase productivity and improve soil coverage.

Interaction between plant roots and beneficial microbiota

The soil hosts several microorganisms that can be highly beneficial to plant growth and health and provide a number of ecosystem services.

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The project is articulated into eight workpackages

1. Management	5. Assessment of product quality (fresh fruit, juice, oil, forage)
2. Isolation and characterization of soil beneficial microbes.	6. Socio-Economic and environmental assessment
3. Technology for inocula production and application.	7. Dissemination
4. Agronomical management of the cropping system for fruit, grain and forage production	8. Training innovation transfer

Social Media

Social network	LINK	TAG
Linktree	https://linktr.ee/prosmallagrimed	@prosmallagrimed
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Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ProSmallAgriMed	@ProSmallAgriMed
Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/prosmallagrimed/	@prosmallagrimed
Linkedin company account	https://www.linkedin.com/company/prosmallagrimed/	#prosmallagrimed @prosmallagrimed
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